

Again I Rise

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I climb with bleeding hands—I climb;
the sky won't bend, won't grant me time.
Each step is heavy, slow, and deep,
each breath a debt I fight to keep.

The peak—so far, it burns my eyes,
a cruel star hung in frozen skies.
It mocks my knees, it counts my slips,
it drinks the salt upon my lips.

I've fallen more than I can say;
the ground has shaped me out of clay.
It bears my weight, it knows my name,
it drinks my tears, it feeds my flame.

But still—"I rise, I rise, I rise";
I sew my wounds, I stitch my cries.
I wash my face in rivers cold,
I grip the rocks with fingers bold.

The summit hides, it turns away—
but I will climb it, come what may.
And when the wind calls out to me,
it will be with the victor's key.

And I will answer—clear, alive:
"I bled, I burned... but I arrived."